

IMPROVING THE READING PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 2-TAURUS THROUGH PROJECT RREF

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ABSTRACT

Unique to humans, reading abilities serve as the primary means of communication in daily life. Due to the disruptions in teaching brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, students in public schools experienced reading learning loss. The researcher conducted a study to deal with these issues. This study used a pre-test post-test research design to evaluate Project RREF's efficacy as an intervention program to improve the reading abilities of Grade Two Taurus students, with the goal of determining the effectiveness of PROJECT RREF to elevate the reading performance of Grade 2 students at Binulasan Integrated School Infanta, Quezon. The 15 pupils in the Grade Two Section Taurus at Binulasan Integrated School, Infanta, Quezon, School Year 2022-2023, in particular, was the focus of the project. The results of the study revealed that the average of reading performance of learners during the pre-test is not good that out of 33 pupils there are 15 or 45% of grade 2 learners fall in frustration and nonreaders. After the implementation of Project RREF, the post-test was conducted. The results denote that the average performance of the class increased at 6.69. There is a significant difference in the reading performance before and after the implementation of Project RREF, which signifies an increase of 10.63 % in the average score from the pre-test to the post-test. This denotes that significant difference in the oral reading performance of Grade Two Taurus pupils before and after the implementation of project RREF was clearly shown. The results proved the effectiveness of remedial reading every Friday and the 30 minutes reading habit before the class start.

Keywords: *reading performance, authentic results, and learning loss*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 outbreak had a global impact on all aspects of human activity, including education, research, and healthcare. Sports, entertainment, transportation, worship, social gatherings/interactions, the economy, businesses, and politics are just a few examples. Indeed, the entire world was in turmoil as a result of COVID-19 threats, and the reality of the situation was difficult to bear. The education sector remains one of the worst-affected by the Coronavirus outbreak (Onyema et.al,2020).

Hares and Mundy (2020) estimated that 91.3 % or 1.57 billion students drop out of school worldwide due to the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition to lost learning time, it is estimated that between 7 and 9.7 million children will drop out of school due to the economic impact of the pandemic (Wagner & Warren, 2020). In another estimate, students can experience learning loss more than one year after three months of school closures because they fall further behind when schools reopen (Kaffenberger, 2021). Chen et al., (2021) explain that students have paid a high price in learning loss, even the impact can be detrimental to the economic well-being of some students throughout their lives.

Furthermore, reading needs students to understand print, recognize distinct sounds in spoken language, and relate those sounds to written letters. They also require extensive background and language knowledge to comprehend the words they read. Finally, learners must be able to instantly recognize most words and read related material effortlessly, paying attention to syntax, punctuation, and sentence structure (Schwartz & Sparks, 2019).

Research looked at how the pandemic affected learning among students in the early grades, and it found noticeable changes in the development of fundamental reading abilities over the course of a year. The results of a reading assessment given to first-through fourth-graders across the country show that students' growth in oral reading fluency, or the ability to read aloud quickly and accurately, slowed significantly in 2020 as a result of the unexpected school closures caused by COVID-19 (Spector, 2021).

Monitoring and Evaluation

Practitioners must naturally be interested in learning how the program functioned and what needed to be improved in order to meet the demands of the learners during monitoring and assessment. Monitoring and evaluation, or M&E, is a crucial component of the attempt to comprehend the efficacy of innovations in a student's learning programming and impact, according to Assefa (2021). Additionally, he claimed that facing challenges and accepting constructive criticism could hinder the success of program execution. However, routine observation ensures that the needs of the students are satisfied. It also provides information on decisions that can be made to improve upon or change original goals or performance levels in the future.

Hasbrouck (2022) further stated that despite the fact that these procedures for screening, diagnosing, progress tracking or monitoring, and evaluation have been around for a while, they haven't been applied regularly in schools (Hasbrouck, et al., 1999). He continued, "This position is likely to change if teachers become more conscious of the value of preventing reading challenges and providing rigorous intervention as soon as a concern is noted." Furthermore, using fluency norms to set appropriate goals for student improvement and monitor progress toward those goals can be a powerful and useful tool for teachers to employ when determining the best course of instruction for their students, particularly the lowest achievers and struggling readers.

Additionally, Gutierrez (2020) used the quasi-experimental method to conduct research on the impact of the monthly monitoring and evaluation on the reading performance of students in grades 1 and 2. The findings showed that pupils in Grades 1 and 2 had considerably better reading skills after the intervention. She came to the conclusion that monitoring and validating monthly reading exams helped students' abilities.

Borreo (2023) conducted a study on the impact of project HEART ME, a reading intervention for learners under frustration level which used extensive reading remediation particularly 30 minutes before the class starts and 30 minutes after the class session ends coupled with Monitoring and Evaluation tools. The findings revealed that there is a positive difference which definitely improved the oral reading performance of elementary pupils in Binulasan Integrated School using the Reading intervention using the project HEART ME. This implied that when pupils are exposed to different reading drills and activities, their reading skills will be amplified.

Meanwhile, the Informal Reading Inventory (IRI), a project of the Schools Division Office in Quezon Province through the Curriculum Implementation Division Instructional Management Section that directly addresses its thrust to make every Quezonian child a reader, was conducted at Binulasan Integrated School when classes for the School Year 2022–2023 opened to all students. Having said that, among the 33 Grade 2 Taurus pupils, 15 students, or 45%, fell into the Non-Reader and Frustration Level in Filipino and English categories. In terms of the school's reading proficiency before to the start and full implementation of face-to-face education, the reading pre-assessment result was extremely alarming.

To address the aforementioned issue, the researcher intended to develop and improve the reading ability of Grade Two Taurus pupils particularly those pupils in Binulasan Integrated School through "Project RREF" (**R**emedial **R**eadin**E** **E**very **F**riday).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectivity of PROJECT RREF to elevate the reading performance of Grade 2 pupils of Binulasan Integrated School Infanta, Quezon through **PROJECT RREF (REMEDIAL READING EVERY FRIDAY)** for the SY:2022-2023.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus before the implementation of PROJECT RREF?
2. What is the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus after the implementation of PROJECT RREF?
3. Is there any significant difference between the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus before and after the implementation of PROJECT RREF?
4. Based on the result of the study, what enhancement in the school's reading program may be developed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a pre-test post-test research design to evaluate Project RREF's efficacy as an intervention program to improve the reading abilities of Grade Two Taurus students. This research method, according to Campbell and Stanley (2001), takes place prior to the actual experiment and establishes how the researcher's intervention will influence the experiment.

Due to its suitability and connection to the study's goals—which concern the effect and influence of the RREF project on Grade Two Taurus readers—the researcher chose this research methodology.

However, the goal of this study is to help Grade 2 students who experience displeasure with their reading performance (slow and nonreaders).

Research Locale

The study will be conducted in Binulasan Integrated School (BIS). The school is located in Infanta District in the Division of Quezon. The school has five sections in Grade two but Grade 2 Taurus pupils are the only respondents. There are 33 Grade 2 pupils, there are 15 pupils or 45% who fall under frustration level in Filipino and in English.

Respondents of the Study

The Grade Two Section Taurus in Binulasan Integrated School, Infanta, Quezon, School Year 2022-2023, specifically those 15 students who exhibit frustration in both Filipino and English, would serve as the study's responders. The approach of purposive sampling was applied. Purposive sampling is a sampling approach in which the researcher uses his or her own judgment to pick people of the population to take part in the study. It is also referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. Purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, is when "elements" picked for the sample are done so using the researcher's discretion. Also, researchers frequently think that by

exercising reasonable judgment they can collect a representative sample (Business Research Methodology, 2014).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the school principal as well as to the parents of the involved pupils before the conduct of the study in improving the reading performance of grade two Taurus pupils who fall from frustration level through "Project RREF" (Remedial Reading Every Friday).

In this study, the researcher used the pretest and posttest in this study to collect the relevant data. Every Friday, the Grade Two adviser conducted the intervention that utilized to boost the students' reading proficiency by extending the permitted reading time. Additionally, the researcher adopted the monitoring instrument that was created by Dr. Ramil A. Borreo and a Phil-IRI evaluation tool to track and assess the learners' reading progress at the conclusion of each quarter. It took place over Three quarters (Second, Third and Fourth Quarter to be exact).

A posttest was performed following the implementation of the "PROJECT RREF" technique. To ascertain whether there has been a significant change in the reading performance of grade two students, the researcher compared the pretest and posttest

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools was used to interpret the data to be gathered.

1. **Weighted Mean.** This was used to determine the average reading performance of Grade Two pupils

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum x$ = summation of weighted frequencies

N = number of cases

To interpret and satisfy the results of the reading performance of Grade Two Taurus-pupils, the Schools Division of Quezon grading scale below in Informal Reading Inventory for grades 1 to 3 will be used and modified by converting mean percentage scores into the weighted mean scores.

Scale	Interpretation
3.01-4.00	Independent
2.77-3.00	Instructional

0.06-2.76 Frustration
 0.00-0.05 non-reader

2. **Paired T-Test.** This was used to analyze and determine the significant difference of the reading performance of Grade Two Taurus pupils of Binulanan Integrated School through "Project RREF" (**Remedial Reading Every Friday**)

The formula is:

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n \sum d^2 - (\sum d)^2}{n - 1}}}$$

Where:

t is the t-value

$\sum d$ is the sum of differences between the pre-test and posttest

$\sum d^2$ is the sum of squared differences between the pre-test and posttest

n is the total number of paired scores

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part includes the discussion of results and reflection of the study. The data presented in this part follows the arrangement of the problems as set in the Action Research Questions. Upon the administration and after the conduct of the examination, the collected data and the result of the pretest and posttest in the second, third and fourth quarter were evaluated and analyzed.

1. What is the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus before the implementation of PROJECT RREF?

Table 1

Level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus Before the Implementation of Project RREF

No. of Pupils	33
Mean	51.64
Standard Deviation	7.19

Table 1 shows the number of pupils, Mean and Standard Deviation before the implementation of Project RREF. The average weighted mean is 51.64 with a standard deviation of 7.19. The results denote that the average performance of the pupils is not good as revealed in the administered pre-test.

According to Kaffenberger (2021), students can experience learning loss more than one year after three months of school closures because they fall further behind when schools reopen.

2. What is the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus after the implementation of PROJECT RREF?

Table 2
Level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus After the Implementation of Project RREF

No. of Pupils	33
Mean	58.67
Standard Deviation	7.66

Table 2 shows presents the number of pupils, Mean and Standard Deviation after the implementation of Project RREF. The average weighted mean is 58.67 with a standard deviation of 7.66. The results denote that the average performance of the pupils is good as revealed in the administered post-test.

The findings of the study is supported by Gutierrez (2020), who conducted a study on the impact of the monthly monitoring and evaluation on the reading performance of students in grades 1 and 2. The findings showed that pupils in Grades 1 and 2 had considerably became better readers after the intervention. She came to the conclusion that monitoring and evaluation and giving an extra time in reading helped the students' abilities improve their reading abilities.

Demonstrating the necessity for intervention programs to assist the 45% of pupils. Hence, Reading plays a significant part in the development of science because reading accounts for the biggest percentage of information transfer (Salaberry, 2001

3. Is there any significant difference between the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus before and after the implementation of PROJECT RREF?

Table 3
Test of Significant Difference between the level of Reading performance of Grade 2-Taurus before and after the implementation of Project RREF

Tests	Average Weighted Mean	P-value	Level of Significance	Decision
Pre-test	51.64	0.00	0.05	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Post-test	58.33			

Table 3 presents the average weighted mean between the reading performance level

of Grade Two Taurus learners in the pre-test, which is 51.64, and 58.33 in the post-test signifies an increase of 6.69. This was found to be significant as supported by the P-value of 0.00 at a 0.05 level of significance.

The result confirms that there is a significant difference in the reading performance of Grade Two Taurus learners of Binulasan Integrated School before and after the implementation of Project RREF.

The findings are supported by the study conducted by The Florida Center for Reading Research as cited by Kafle (2017) advises ninety (90) minutes of literacy instruction for schools with a high percentage of students at risk for reading challenges; this time should be altered as necessary to accommodate the changing requirements of students. Therefore, the more reading exercises and activities that kids who have reading challenges are exposed to over time, the better their reading skills will be strengthened.

4. Based on the result of the study, what enhancement in the school’s reading program may be developed?

Inputs to Improve the reading performance of Grade Two

Proposed Enhanced Program

Key Results Area	Specific Objective	Strategy	Persons Involved	Materials Needed	Time Frame	Expected Output	Budget
Remedial Reading Every Friday	To encourage ongoing improvement of students' reading abilities	-Before class there is a 30-minute reading period. And remedial reading every Friday.	Teachers -School heads -Master Teachers	-Printed Reading Materials -Laptop Television	Year Round	100 % Readers	1000

Conclusions

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations. The summary of findings follows the order of the statement of the problem in chapter 1. Based on the findings extracted from the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Before the implementation of Project RREF, out of 33 students there are 15 or 45% students who fall under frustration and nonreader level in Filipino and in English due to pandemic.
2. After the implementation of Project RREF for 7 months, it was concluded that the reading performance of grade two Taurus learners at was improved. There are 31 or 93.39% students who belong to Instructional and Independent readers.
3. It was highly evident that there is a significant difference in the reading performance of grade two taurus learners before and after the implementation of Project RREF. Remedial reading every Friday and 30 minutes reading habit before the class start are effective ways for improving the reading performance of learners.
4. Due to the pandemic, the majority of students experienced learning loss, particularly in reading, thus teachers need to take action to help students develop their reading abilities in fun and engaging ways.

Recommendations

In light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the following are hereby recommended:

1. For learners

- a. Request the assistance of a parent or other trusted adult while reading words in unfamiliar reading materials to improve their reading abilities.
- b. Learners should continue practicing their reading skills even at home.

2. For the Teachers

- a. Plan and carry out initiatives like remedial classes and other innovations that would improve the students' reading skills even further.
- b. Towards the end of the fourth quarter, engage in more intensive reading remediation exercises.
- c. The designed project proposal may be adopted by other teachers, to improve the reading performance of the learners.

3. For school administrators

- a. The school head of the school may allot funds from MOOE or the local budget for the preparation, planning, and execution of upcoming programs at various grade levels.
- b. Encourage the teachers to participate in trainings and seminars that will improve their teaching skills.

4. For Future researchers

For more conclusive results, they could replicate this study and do further future investigation on this Improving Reading Performance in other districts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher sought permission from the school's principal and parents of the involved pupils. The researcher also promised to keep the participants' identities and personal information anonymous and secret.

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